

Kinetics of Polymerisation of Tungstic Acid and the Effect of Ethanol on the Process

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The polymerisation of tungstic acid molecules in aqueous medium, prepared by ion-exchange method, is a condensation polymerisation reaction of the third order.

There is retardation of turbidity with the increase of molecular ratio of ethanol to water. A quantitative explanation has been attempted on the basis of formation of a complex between tungstic acid and ethanol.

The polyacidic nature of tungstic acid in solution has been studied by several authors. Britton¹ has investigated the acidic nature of the oxide (WO_3) by electrometric titration of a solution of the oxide in sodium hydroxide with hydrochloric acid. In order to determine the composition of the poly-anions of tungstic acids at different pH, Jander and co-workers², Brintzinger³, and Souchay⁴ have studied their rates of diffusion and dialysis. They have shown that there are several poly-anions and for stability of each, there is a characteristic range of pH. Mitra and Chari⁵ have prepared tungstic acid solution by ion-exchange method and titrated it by potassium hydroxide potentiometrically. They have obtained two inflection points, the first one being at 25% of the total acid given by the second inflection point.

Ghosh and Dhar⁶ observed that tungstic acid sols became turbid, more viscous, less conducting, and more unstable on ageing. They ascribed the increase of viscosity and decrease of conductance of tungstic acid sol with time to the aggregation of the dissolved molecules to form more colloidal particles. While studying the optical properties of clear tungstic acid sol, prepared by using ion-exchange resin according to the method of Mitra and Chari⁵, it has been observed by us that the clear sol soon develops turbidity which first increases with time and then decreases as the big aggregates settle down. After some time, however, the turbidity was again found to increase. From this observation, it has been inferred that the process is not the same as the usual coagulation of a colloid. It has been shown on further investigation to be a condensation polymerisation reaction⁷.

The effect of ethanol on tungstic acid sol has been studied by several workers. Wassiljewa⁸ found that tungstic acid could be reduced to blue-coloured sol by ethanol, glucose, etc. Ghosh and Bhattacharya⁹ have studied the photochemical reduction of the sols of tungstic acid and molybdic acid by ethanol. It has been observed by us that in the

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 147.
2. *Kolloid Beihfte*, 1934, 41, 1, 297; 1942, 54, 1; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, 190, 195; 1939, 185, 325; 1941, 188, 65; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 187, 60.
3. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1935, 224, 97.
4. *Ann. chim.*, 1943, 18, 61, 169; *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1947, 14, 914.
5. *Symp. High Polymers*, Calcutta, 1960, 30-31, 17.
6. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 1908.
7. Ghosh *et al.*, *Science & Culture*, 1962, 28, 244.
8. *Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1913, 12, 1.
9. *This Journal*, 1930, 7, 716.

absence of light, addition of ethanol causes no reduction of the clear tungstic acid sol prepared by ion-exchange method, but the rate of development of turbidity is decreased.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium tungstate ($\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) of A. R. quality, E. Merck was used as the starting material. The tungstate was dissolved in double-distilled water. This solution was percolated through a 20 cm column of the resin, IR-120(H), at a slow rate, the amount (in ml) percolated being about one-third of the total exchange capacity of the resin in order to obtain total conversion. A clear solution of tungstic acid of pH nearly 2.2 was thus obtained. Analysis of this tungstic acid sol showed absence of sodium, indicating purity of the sol to a fair degree.

Condensation of Tungstic Acid in Water

A definite volume of a freshly prepared solution of tungstic acid was taken in each of a number of tall pyrex glass bottles and these were kept in a thermostat at a constant temperature. After a definite interval, a known volume of the solution was withdrawn from the first bottle, centrifuged, and the concentration of tungstic oxide (WO_3) in the clear supernatant solution was determined. This process was repeated with the other bottles in succession at regular intervals. The plot of time against the reciprocal of the square of WO_3 concentration yielded a straight line (Fig. 1). The condensation polymerisation of tungstic acid in aqueous solution therefore is a reaction of the third order.

FIG. 1

Effect of Ethanol on the Rate of Increase of Turbidity of Tungstic Acid Solution

The increase of turbidity of tungstic acid solution in presence of ethanol was followed by measuring the intensity of scattered light.

A freshly prepared tungstic acid solution was filtered through Corning fine glass filters (15 microns) in order to eliminate avoidable optical impurities causing considerable error through additional scattering. A definite volume of the solution was pipetted out and quickly poured into a pyrex bottle containing a known volume of a mixture of water and ethanol. This process was repeated with a series of bottles in which the pro-

portion of the constituents was varied. Hence the concentration of WO_3 remained the same in each bottle, which was kept tightly stoppered.

FIG. 2

The increase in turbidity with time of four sols, having the same percentage concentration of WO_3 but different proportion of tungstic acid to water, was measured in a Brice-Phoenix Universal light scattering photometer. As tungstic acid in the medium of H_2O -EtOH absorbed very little light at all wave lengths between $540 m\mu$ and $600 m\mu$, the wave length of $546 m\mu$ was used. Along with all turbidity measurements, the dissymmetry was always measured. From these dissymmetry values and theoretical curve for rod (variation of correction factor $1/p_{90^\circ}$ with dissymmetry Z)¹⁰, the correction factors were found and multiplication of apparent turbidity by the correction factor provided the corrected turbidity. The results are shown in Fig. 2 [curves *a*, *b*, *c*, and *d* correspond to Stacey, "Light Scattering in Physical Chemistry", Table IV, p. 63, 1956.

pond to scale (a), (b), (c), and (d) respectively]. The electron micrograph of tungstic acid sol was obtained by Watson *et al.*¹¹ and found to be needle shaped.

Calculations of turbidity and dissymmetry were worked out according to the direction given in the literature supplied by the Brice-Phoenix Instrument Company. Refractive index measurements were made with an Abbe refractometer. Incidentally, all measurements for turbidity and dissymmetry were carried out to the stage when a faint precipitate just appeared. All measurements were taken at 25°.

It has been observed that at the equiturbidity point, the plot of square root of time (t) against the molecular ratio of ethanol to water (m_a/m_w) gives a straight line. This will be evident from Fig. 3.

FIG. 3

DISCUSSION

The third order polymerisation reaction of tungstic acid may be accounted for by assuming that two hydroxyl groups, one from each of two molecules of tungstic acid,

react and another hydroxyl group of one of the reacting molecules or of a different molecule acts as a catalyst. The reaction is therefore similar to the condensation polymerisation of glycols with adipic acid, observed by Flory¹², in the absence of any added catalyst.

It will be observed from Fig. 2, that there is retardation of turbidity as the proportion of ethanol is increased. For a fixed WO_3 concentration in the sol, a linear relationship is obtained between $\sqrt{t}$ (t is the time at the equiturbidity point) and molecular ratio of ethanol to water. This can be accounted for by assuming that: (i) tungstic acid forms a complex with ethanol according to the equation

and (ii) this (Complex) does not polymerise.

Therefore, when the system consisting of H_2WO_4 , EtOH , (Complex), and H_2O attains equilibrium, we have

$$\frac{[(\text{Complex})]}{[(\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4)_f]} = k \frac{[\text{EtOH}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} .$$

where $(\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4)_f$ denotes free (H_2WO_4)

$$\text{or} \quad [(\text{Complex})] = k \frac{[\text{EtOH}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} [(\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4)_f] \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Now, it may be assumed that (Complex) and $(\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4)_f$ together constitute the whole of initial $[\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4]_i$ taken. Therefore, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4]_i &= [(\text{Complex})] + [(\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4)_f] \\ &= k \frac{[\text{EtOH}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} [(\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4)_f] + [(\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4)_f] \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{or} \quad [(\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4)_f] = [\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4]_i / \left\{ 1 + k \frac{[\text{EtOH}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \right\} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Hence, concentration of H_2WO_4 available for polymerisation is

$$[\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4]_i / \left\{ 1 + k \frac{[\text{EtOH}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \right\}$$

Now, for the third-order condensation polymerisation reaction, the time (t), required for the conversion of a definite fraction of the ~~total~~ amount of the monomer taken into polymer, may be written as

$$t = \frac{1}{k_1 c^2}$$

where c is the concentration of the monomer present at the time t . Since the reaction is of the third order, as shown previously, and since the same turbidity may be taken to

represent approximately the conversion of the same fraction of monomer, initially present, into polymer, we can replace c by $[(H_2WO_4)_t]$. We therefore write

$$t = \frac{1}{k_i [(H_2WO_4)_t]^n} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Now, putting the value of $[(H_2WO_4)_t]$ from equation (3) in equation (4) we get

$$t = \frac{\left\{ 1 + k \frac{[EtOH]}{[H_2O]} \right\}^2}{k_i [(H_2WO_4)_i]^2}$$

or

$$\sqrt{t} = \frac{1 + k \frac{[EtOH]}{[H_2O]}}{\sqrt{k_i} [(H_2WO_4)_i]} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

Hence a plot of $\sqrt{t}$ against $[EtOH]/[H_2O]$ will be linear.

The intercepts of the straight lines corresponding to conversion represented by the turbidities 0.2, 0.12, and 0.08 are 0.7, 0.66, and 0.6 respectively. The values of k found by dividing the slope of the straight lines by the corresponding intercepts are 85.7, 81.8, and 83.3 respectively. The average of these values 83.6 may be taken as the mean value of k .

We may conclude that with the increase of the proportion of ethanol to water, more and more tungstic acid is consumed in the formation of a complex which reduces the effective concentration of tungstic acid and hence retards the increase of turbidity.

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